

Neural Network-Based Triangle Culling for BVH Traversal: A Negative Result

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Abstract

We investigate whether lightweight neural networks can accelerate BVH traversal by predicting ray-triangle *misses* before running the Möller-Trumbore (MT) intersection test. We perform an exhaustive neural architecture search (3,424 feature-architecture combinations; 1,826 trained models) under a ≤ 45 -FLOP budget, selecting a decision threshold on validation to maximize cull rate subject to $\geq 95\%$ cull precision. World-space baselines cull 1.38% of triangles at 100% validation precision, but drop to 80% precision on held-out test. Rotation normalization improves validation culling to 2.95% (97.1% precision) yet still fails to generalize (1.73% cull at 92.0% test precision). Adding distance scaling yields the best validation result: 5.81% cull at 95.5% precision, but test precision falls to 89.4% at 4.58% cull. Because our best models cost 32–44 FLOPs per candidate triangle while MT is ≈ 35 FLOPs, FLOP-based break-even is impossible for models with $F_{\text{NN}} \geq F_{\text{MT}}$ and would require $> 91\%$ culling even for a 32-FLOP network at perfect precision. We conclude that small MLPs do not provide cost-effective triangle culling in this setting.

1 Introduction

Ray tracing performance is dominated by ray-primitive intersection tests during BVH traversal, typically accelerated using bounding volume hierarchies (BVHs) [4]. The Möller-Trumbore (MT) algorithm [1] requires approximately 35 floating-point operations per triangle, creating a natural question: can a cheaper learned model predict definite misses, allowing us to skip the full intersection test?

We formalize this as a binary classification problem. Given geometric features extractable *before* the MT test (bounding box parameters, triangle properties, ray direction), predict whether the ray will miss.

1.1 Metric Definitions

We define the following metrics used throughout:

- **Cull rate** $r = P(\hat{y} = \text{miss})$: fraction of triangles predicted as misses and therefore skipped

- **Cull precision** $p = P(y = \text{miss} \mid \hat{y} = \text{miss})$: probability that a culled triangle is a true miss (i.e., precision on the culled set)
- **Hit recall** $= P(\hat{y} = \text{hit} \mid y = \text{hit})$: probability that true hits are correctly identified (not incorrectly culled)

A viable culling solution requires: (1) high cull rate r , (2) high cull precision $p \geq 95\%$ to avoid rendering artifacts, and (3) total computational cost below baseline.

1.2 Cost Model and Break-Even Analysis

The per-triangle cost when using a neural culling network is:

$$C_{\text{total}} = F_{\text{NN}} + (1 - r) \cdot F_{\text{MT}} \quad (1)$$

where F_{NN} is the network’s FLOP cost and $F_{\text{MT}} \approx 35$ is the MT test cost. We run the network on every triangle, then perform MT only on triangles predicted as potential hits.

Break-even requires $C_{\text{total}} < F_{\text{MT}}$:

$$F_{\text{NN}} + (1 - r) \cdot F_{\text{MT}} < F_{\text{MT}} \quad (2)$$

$$r > \frac{F_{\text{NN}}}{F_{\text{MT}}} \quad (3)$$

For our best-performing architecture (44 FLOPs):

$$r > \frac{44}{35} \approx 1.26 \quad (4)$$

Since $r \leq 1$ by definition, **FLOP-based break-even is impossible** for any model with $F_{\text{NN}} \geq F_{\text{MT}}$. For example, our best validation model in Experiment 3 uses $F_{\text{NN}} = 44$ FLOPs, implying $r > 44/35 \approx 1.26$. Even the cheapest networks we consider ($F_{\text{NN}} = 32$) would require $r > 32/35 \approx 0.914$ culling at *perfect* precision—far beyond any observed performance.

Note: One might argue that MT is “expensive” for reasons beyond raw FLOPs (branch divergence, memory access patterns, etc.). If the effective cost of MT were higher—say, 80 equivalent FLOPs—then break-even would require $r > 44/80 = 55\%$. However, under any reasonable accounting where the neural network also incurs similar overheads, the fundamental problem remains: our networks are not substantially cheaper than MT.

Table 1: Dataset statistics for the high-detail experiment suite.

Statistic	Value
BVH leaves	38,764
Leaf samples	5,681
Total triangles	408,720
Final samples	100,000

2 Related Work

BVHs are the dominant acceleration structure for ray tracing in both offline and real-time rendering, and their construction and traversal have been extensively surveyed [4]. At the leaf level, ray-triangle intersection is commonly computed using the Möller-Trumbore algorithm [1] (or close variants), while end-to-end performance is shaped by factors beyond raw FLOPs—SIMT divergence, memory behavior, and traversal order—especially on GPUs [2]. High-performance implementations such as Embree demonstrate how careful kernel design and vectorization are critical for practical throughput on CPUs [3].

A separate line of work explores *learned* components in the ray tracing pipeline. For example, Liu et al. propose predicting intersections to skip redundant traversal work on GPUs [5]. More recently, N-BVH replaces portions of explicit geometry with a compact learned representation that answers ray queries while retaining BVH-like empty-space skipping [6]. These methods are typically not limited to a per-candidate-triangle, pre-MT feature set.

In contrast, our goal is deliberately narrow: we ask whether a *tiny* MLP (under a ≤ 45 -FLOP budget) can classify *misses* using only features available before executing MT. This yields a clean cost model, but also makes the negative result interpretable: if pre-intersection geometric features contain insufficient information for high-precision miss prediction, then adding a similarly-priced classifier in front of MT is unlikely to help.

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset Generation

We sample ray-triangle pairs from high-detail 3D models (60K–160K triangles). Five models are placed randomly within 5 units of the camera origin with random rotations, using time-seeded RNG to eliminate sampling bias. BVH leaf nodes are sampled with $p = 0.001$ probability.

Models are scaled such that bounding volumes span 3–64 cubic units, controlling for scale variance.

We restrict the feature set to quantities computable *before* MT; in particular we exclude MT intermediates/outputs (e.g., t, u, v and raw barycentric terms such

as u_raw, v_raw) to avoid label leakage.

3.2 Class Imbalance Correction

Raw data exhibits severe imbalance: approximately 3% hits and 97% misses. This causes networks to converge to trivial “always predict miss” strategies with near-zero loss but no discriminative power. We apply stratified resampling to achieve 40% hits / 60% misses, forcing networks to learn discriminative features. Unless stated otherwise, validation and test splits are drawn from this resampled distribution, so absolute cull rates are reported relative to the resampled prior; in deployment, thresholds should be re-tuned under the true hit/miss prior.

3.3 Neural Architecture Search

We perform exhaustive NAS over 3,424 feature-architecture combinations:

- **Input features** ($n = 7$ – 10): Selected from 18 candidates (see Table 2)
- **Hidden layers** (L): 1–2 layers
- **Hidden units** (H): 2 neurons per layer
- **Cost constraint**: Total FLOPs ≤ 45

Table 2: Feature abbreviations used in experiments

Abbrev.	Description
aabb	Axis-aligned bounding box (6 values)
area	Triangle area
inrad	Inscribed circle radius
circumrad	Circumscribed circle radius
asp	Aspect ratio
det	Determinant (ray-triangle)
ori	Orientation sign
ray_dir	Ray direction vector (3 values)
dot_v0/v1/v2	Dot product with vertex vectors
incenter	Triangle incenter (3 values)
circumcenter	Circumcenter (3 values)
fermat	Fermat point (3 values)
unit_norm	Unit normal vector (3 values)
ray_norm_dot	Ray-normal dot product

Models are trained with binary cross-entropy loss. We select probability thresholds on validation data that maximize cull rate r subject to cull precision $p \geq 95\%$, then evaluate on held-out test sets.

4 Experiments and Results

4.1 Experiment 1: Baseline (No Geometric Preprocessing)

Using world-space coordinates without preprocessing, the best model achieves only **1.38% VAL cull rate** at 100%

Table 3: Top models from Experiment 2 (rotation normalization). Reported as cull rate / cull precision. Feature lists are wrapped to fit the column.

Rank	Arch	Features	VAL	TEST
1	8-1-2	area, incenter, ori, ray_dir	2.95% / 97.1%	1.73% / 92.0%
2	7-1-2	area, incenter, ray_dir	2.08% / 95.8%	1.60% / 91.3%
3	8-1-2	asp, circumcenter, ori, ray_dir	2.08% / 95.8%	2.22% / 90.6%
4	10-1-2	aabb, inrad, ray_dir	1.82% / 95.2%	2.08% / 93.3%

Table 4: Top models from Experiment 3 (rotation + scaling). Reported as cull rate / cull precision. Long feature lists are wrapped to fit the column.

Arch	Features	VAL	TEST
10-1-2	aabb, inrad, ray_dir	5.81% / 95.5%	4.58% / 89.4%
8-1-2	asp, dot_v1, incenter, ray_dir	5.64% / 95.4%	4.93% / 85.9%
9-1-2	det, inrad, ori, ray_dir, unit_norm	3.73% / 95.4%	2.98% / 81.4%
7-1-2	asp, fermat, ray_dir	2.78% / 96.9%	2.78% / 87.5%
7-1-2	asp, det, dot_v1, inrad, ray_dir	1.91% / 95.5%	2.43% / 91.4%

VAL cull precision; on test it still culls 1.38% but precision drops to 80%. This poor performance occurs because the same triangle at different world-space orientations produces entirely different feature vectors despite identical geometric hit/miss relationships.

4.2 Experiment 2: Rotation Normalization

We pre-rotate all geometry such that the BVH face orthogonal to the z-axis is intersected at $(0, 0, z)$. This canonicalizes the coordinate frame relative to the ray-BVH intersection. The rotation matrix can be pre-computed and stored per BVH node; at runtime, only the ray direction requires rotation (3 values vs. 9 for triangle vertices).

Result: Best VAL cull rate improves to **2.95%** ($2.14\times$ over baseline).

4.3 Experiment 3: Rotation + Distance Scaling

We additionally scale the ray direction vector such that its magnitude equals the distance from the origin to the triangle’s v_0 vertex. This normalizes the “depth” component, making the network’s task scale-invariant.

Result: Best VAL cull rate reaches **5.81%** ($4.21\times$ over baseline).

The sharp performance drop-off (rank 1: 5.81% vs. rank 20: 0.69%) indicates high sensitivity to architecture—most configurations fail to learn useful representations.

4.4 Experiment 4: Low-Detail Models

We test on simpler geometry (300–9,000 triangles, 21 models) expecting potentially cleaner decision boundaries.

Result: Performance *decreases*. The best low-detail model reaches **2.22% VAL cull** at 100% VAL precision, but its held-out test precision falls to **82.9%** while culling 2.31% of triangles. This suggests that the dominant failure mode is not solely geometric complexity, but distribution shift and limited separability in the pre-intersection feature space.

5 Analysis

5.1 Generalization Gap

All experiments exhibit significant validation-to-test degradation. The best model from Experiment 3 drops from 95.5% to 89.4% cull precision—a 6.1 percentage point decrease. Across the top 20 VAL-selected models in Experiment 3, precision drops range from 5 to over 50 percentage points. Only 2 of these 20 models maintained $\geq 95\%$ precision on test data (and both culled $< 1\%$ of triangles).

5.2 Learned Representations

Output probability distributions consistently show bimodal structure: one peak around $p \approx 0.4$ (predominantly misses) and one around $p \approx 0.55$ (predominantly hits). However, both peaks contain substantial contamination from the opposite class. The mean predicted probability for hits vs. misses differs by only 0.01–0.08, confirming weak discriminative signal.

5.3 Why This Approach Fails

The ray-triangle intersection condition requires finding t, u, v satisfying:

$$\vec{o} + t\vec{d} = v_0 + u(v_1 - v_0) + v(v_2 - v_0) \quad (5)$$

with constraints $t > 0$, $u \geq 0$, $v \geq 0$, and $u + v \leq 1$ (barycentric coordinates within the triangle).

The features available *before* performing this test—AABB bounds, triangle center points, inradius, ray direction—contain only coarse volumetric information. They cannot encode the precise spatial relationship between a 1D ray and a 2D manifold embedded in 3D space. Within our explored architecture space (≤ 45 FLOPs, 1–2 hidden layers, 18 feature types), no configuration achieves a useful precision-cull tradeoff.

6 Summary

We summarize the best-performing configuration from each experiment suite and compare against the FLOP-

Table 5: Summary of results across all experiments.

Method	VAL Cull	TEST Cull	×Base
Baseline (raw)	1.38%	1.38%	1.00
+ Rotation	2.95%	1.73%	2.14
+ Rotation + Scaling	5.81%	4.58%	4.21
Low-detail models (separate dataset)	2.22%	2.31%	–
<i>Required (32 FLOP net)</i>	<i>>91%</i>	<i>–</i>	<i>> 66</i>

based break-even requirement derived in Section 1.2. Across all settings, validation-selected models fail to maintain the target $\geq 95\%$ cull precision on held-out tests unless they cull an operationally negligible fraction of triangles.

7 Conclusion

Neural network-based triangle culling is not cost-effective for accelerating BVH traversal. The fundamental barrier is computational: networks cheap enough to provide savings (<35 FLOPs) lack the capacity to learn useful representations, while networks with sufficient capacity cost more than the MT test they aim to replace. Even setting aside computational costs, our best cull rate (5.81% VAL, 4.58% TEST) falls far short of practical utility.

Within the explored architecture space, pre-MT features cannot encode the barycentric relationships required for accurate miss prediction. Future work might explore learned BVH construction, approximate rendering applications where lower precision is acceptable, or hybrid importance sampling methods—though our results suggest fundamental limitations for the direct culling approach.

References

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